

AE MONITORING OF MICRODAMAGES IN 3D-WOVEN SiC/SiC COMPOSITES UNDER THERMAL STRESS INDUCED BY DIRECT DIODE LASER IRRADIATION

T. HAYASHI and S. WAKAYAMA
Tokyo Metropolitan University
1-1 Minami-Osawa Hachioji, Tokyo, 192-0397
wakayama@tmu.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

The thermal shock test method using a direct diode laser (DDL) with 4ch AE monitoring was developed to investigate the thermal stress fracture behavior in SiC/SiC composites. The thermal stress was induced by the shading method, which generated a circular shadow at the central portion of a square sample during rapidly heating with the DDL. In order to assess microdamage due to thermal stress, the acoustic emission (AE) signals were monitored during the test. The surface temperature distribution was measured by using infrared cameras. The distribution data was then used to conduct the transient thermal stress analysis using FEM. It was shown that the temperature distribution produced a biaxial tensile stress field at the center of the sample. The AE activity increased with increasing the thermal stress. The nucleation time and location of microdamages due to thermal stress were well detected by AE monitoring. Thus it was demonstrated that the developed thermal shock test can evaluate the thermal stress fracture behavior of the 3D-woven SiC/SiC composites.

Keywords: *Acoustic Emission, SiC/SiC Composite, Thermal Shock Test, Thermal Stress, Laser*

1. INTRODUCTION

SiC/SiC composites have been studied for high-temperature components in aircraft jet engines such as turbine nozzles [1], shrouds [2] and several afterburner parts [1,3]. Since those components are repeatedly subjected to severe thermal shocks during use, the thermal shock behavior of SiC/SiC composites must be investigated. The authors evaluated the strength degradation of the 3D-woven SiC/SiC composites under thermal cycles with burner-rig tests [4]. Consequently, it was found that the strength degradation can possibly result from microdamages due to thermal stress in tension. The thermal stress fracture behavior is considered to be an accumulation of microdamages caused by unsteady and ununiform temperature distribution. Thus the interpretation of the fracture behavior must be based on the simultaneous evaluation of microdamage progression and the thermal stress field. However, since it is difficult with the burner rig test to identify the time and location of any microdamage and to estimate complex and rapidly changing thermal stress distribution, the burner rig test cannot well analyze thermal stress fracture behavior. Thus, a thermal shock test, which corresponds to a cycle of the burner-rig test, must first be established to evaluate both the damage progression and the thermal stress. In our previous study, which included the burner-rig test, the

SiC/SiC composites predominantly exhibited tensile fractures due to mechanical or thermal loading [4,5]. Thus, the fracture behavior of the SiC/SiC composites must be evaluated with tensile thermal stress.

One of the most popular thermal shock tests is the water quench test [6], in which 2D-SiC/SiC composites were evaluated [7,8]. However it was difficult for the water quench test to detect damage and estimate thermal stress. On the other hand, the Disc-on-Rod test, which was developed by the author [9], can simultaneously evaluate the microdamage progression and thermal stress. A circular thin sample was heated by an infrared lamp, and then was quenched at the central region by a circular copper rod with a flat contact surface at ambient temperature. Since transient thermal temperature distribution was measured by an IR-camera, the stress distribution can be accurately obtained. An equiaxial tensile stress field can be produced by the test method at the central region of the sample. The microdamage behavior can be monitored by a one-channel AE sensor attached under the copper rod. A previous study showed the crack growth behavior of the alumina during thermal shock with the Disc-on-Rod test [9]. However, the 3D-woven composites cannot be sufficiently quenched. Since the composites have no flat surface, the thermal contact resistance with the copper rod was too large. Thus this study developed a new thermal shock test which utilized laser and shade instead of a contact method.

The purpose of this study was to develop a thermal shock test method which can detect the nucleation time and location of the microdamages, and estimate the thermal stress directly with the measurement of surface temperatures. The thermal stress fracture behavior of the 3D-woven SiC/SiC composites was investigated with this method.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials and Specimens

The SiC/SiC composites used in this study were made of Tyranno™ ZMI SiC (Si-C-O-Zr) fiber of Ube Industries Ltd., and SiC matrices. The weaving structure of the SiC/SiC composite used in this study is of a three-dimensional (3D) orthogonal architecture with a 2mm pitch in 7 layers as schematically shown in Fig. 1 (a). The 3D-woven architecture consists of three layers of X bundles, four layers of Y bundles and Z bundles. The fiber content ratio along X, Y and Z axes is 1:1:0.2 (volume fraction ratio is 18%:18%:4%). Each bundle has 1600 filaments of the SiC fibers.

Using the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) process, a carbon interface layer was first coated on the fibers to control the fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength. Then, the preforms were densified with SiC derived from methyltrichlorosilane by the CVI process and from polycarbosilane by four cycles of the polymer impregnation pyrolysis (PIP) process. Finally, the preforms were coated with a layer of CVI-SiC of ~10 μm in thickness to protect the surface from oxidation and then cut to the final dimension of the specimen. The dimension of the specimen was 15 mm square and approximately 2 mm thickness.

Figure 1 (b) shows a cross-sectional view of the YZ plane along “aa”. The material composition near the surface is also depicted in the figure. Due to the woven structure the upper and bottom surfaces are not flat, which will result in a notch-like geometry,

Fig. 1. Schematic diagrams of 3D-woven SiC/SiC composites showing woven architecture in (a) and material composition in (b).

producing stress concentration. The location of the notch-like geometry is indicated by a gray arrow, and is called a “corner” in this paper.

The volume fractions of fiber, matrix and porosity were 41%, 34% and 25%, respectively. The matrix volume fraction was calculated by the matrix density ($\sim 2 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and the matrix weight measured before and after the densification of the matrix.

2.2 Experimental Procedures

2.2.1 Thermal Stress Loading

The thermal shock was applied in air by the laser irradiation with a shading method. The concept of the shading method is schematically shown in Fig. 2; (a) Laser light is irradiated on the surface of the specimen and the shade is placed between the laser light source and the specimen. Then, a circular shadow can be projected on the central area of the specimen, which prevents heating the central region of the sample. (b) The outer region's temperature difference compared to the central region was great. (c) The thermal mismatch can induce a balanced biaxial thermal stress in tension at the central region of the sample.

Figure 3 shows the schematic diagram of the thermal shock test system. Four spring-loaded rods of stainless steel supported the specimen. The CO_2 laser has been widely used as a heating device to generate thermal shock in high heat-resistant materials [10,11]. However, since these lasers have the gaussian laser profile which concentrates the beam at the center, it appears that these lasers were not applicable to heat a wide area with uniform heat flux. On the other hand, the direct diode laser (DDL) has a top-hat laser profile which can uniformly heat over a relatively large area. Thus this study utilized the direct diode laser (NUVONYX, ISL2000L) as the heating device. The laser light was focused into $\sim 30 \text{ mm}$ squares by multiple stages of lenses. The circular shadow was created by an ellipse-shaped ceramic shade, which shielded against the focused light beams of the laser. The elliptical shape was empirically determined so that a circular shadow with $\sim 6 \text{ mm}$ diameter was projected onto the specimen. The

Fig. 2. Schematic diagrams of the shading method.

Fig. 3. Experimental set-up of the thermal shock test.

shade was fixed with a platinum wire of 0.3 mm diameter. The ceramic shade was schematically shown in Fig.4(a). The waveguide of the SUS 304 rods was also shown in Fig.4(b). The laser was irradiated for 2 seconds at 1.56kW(70A) power. The laser power was measured by a power sensor (Coherent, LM-2500). The specimen was cooled at ambient temperature.

2.2.2 Temperature measurement

The surface temperature distribution was measured by using two infrared cameras, which data was then used to conduct the transient heat transfer analysis using FEM (code: ANSYS7.1). The FEM model was shown in Fig. 5. In the FEM model, hexahedral elements with 8 nodes were utilized. The coordinate axis was cylindrical with the origin at the center of the specimen as shown in Fig. 5. The internal temperature distribution was calculated only with the measured surface-temperature distributions, without taking into account the uncertain heat transfer coefficient between sample and air. The temperature measurements without uncertainty can allow us to estimate the thermal stress distribution with higher accuracy.

(a) Schematic of ceramic shade.

(b) Schematic of stainless (SUS304) rod.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagrams of the ceramic shade and the waveguide.

Fig. 5. FEM model.

The temperature dependences of thermal properties had significant effects on the thermal stress, and then the analysis was carried out using the functions that were obtained from linear interpolation of the temperature dependent data. The material parameters were shown in the Table 1. In addition, the Poisson's ratio was assumed to be 0.2.

In order to neglect the heat transfer rate between the specimen and stainless steel rod, the thickness of the specimen was chosen to be small. Thus, the four side surfaces were supposed to be thermally insulated. The calculated internal temperature distributions were then input to a mechanical element

Table 1 Parameters used in the FEM analysis (slope and intercept).

x^*	a^*	b^*
Elastic Modulus [GPa]	-5.3×10^{-3} [GPaK ⁻¹]	98 [GPa]
Specific Heat [J g ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	4.9×10^{-4} [J g ⁻¹ K ⁻²]	7.7×10^{-1} [J g ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
Thermal Conductivity [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	1.4×10^{-4} [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻²]	3.6 [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion [K ⁻¹]	2.1×10^{-9} [K ⁻²]	3.2×10^{-6} [K ⁻¹]

$$* x = a(T - 273) + b, \text{ (Temperature : } T \text{ [K])}$$

model to analyze the transient thermal stress. The spring force for the fixation of the specimen was small and it was neglected in the stress analysis.

2.2.3 AE monitoring

During the tests, the AE signals emitted from the sample were monitored simultaneously by four highly sensitive AE sensors with the FET (field effect transistor) head amplifiers (resonance frequency, ~200 kHz). In order to measure the AE signals under a high temperature environment, the location of the AE sensors must take into account the following 2 factors: 1) Since the thermal capability of the AE sensor is low, heat insulation between the specimen and the AE sensor is needed, which prevents from attaching the AE sensor directly to the specimen, 2) The intensity of the AE signals, which are often measured by the signal amplitude, decreases with increasing the distance to the sample. Thus, the AE sensor should be attached to the sample as close as possible, without violating the heat insulation condition. In this study, four spring-loaded rods supported the specimen to satisfy these conditions. The rods were assumed to work as a heat protection for the AE sensor and a waveguide of the AE signal. The AE signal from the micro-damages in the specimen due to thermal stress can be transmitted by four rods and detected by four AE sensors. The AE signals were amplified by 55 dB and then were transmitted to the AE analyzer. The threshold level was set to 31.6 mV at the input terminal of the AE analyzer. The AE location was calculated by the arrival time difference of the wavefront, which was manually measured from the AE signals. This method improves the accuracy of estimating the AE location. The anisotropic characteristic of the sound velocity was taken into account when calculating the AE location.

2.2.4 Microdamage observation

The specimen used in the thermal shock test was cut and observed with SEM. The cross sections for the observation were selected among the locations where a relatively large AE signal was located. After the thermal shock test, the specimen was soaked in an epoxy resin (GATAN, G2). After the epoxy resin hardened, the specimens were cut with a diamond cutter. The cut surface in the XZ-plane was polished by a 16 μm diamond sheet and then polished by an argon-ion beam (JEOL, SM-09010). The

advantages of this polishing method are 1) smooth surface with no processing strain, 2) applicable for materials having several constituents with different hardness. In order to remove the section mechanically damaged, a depth of $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ was polished off by the argon-ion beam. The cross sections were observed using a scanning electron microscope.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Temperature distribution

Figure 6 shows the temperature distribution of heated side's surface at $t = 2 \text{ s}$ (t : elapsed time, the laser irradiation was initiated at $t = 0 \text{ s}$). The inhomogeneous distribution of temperature was observed in the outer region where the laser was irradiated. However, the temperature of the outer region was quite elevated compared to the shaded inner region, which confirmed that the shading method was effective to give large thermal gradient. The maximum temperature of the sample reached $1435 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The trends of the temperature variation along a diagonal path A-C were shown at intervals of 0.4 second in Fig.7. The temperature difference ΔT between the averaged temperature of two peaks, T_1 , and the minimum temperature, T_2 , showed a maximum value of approximately $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at $t = 2.0 \text{ s}$.

Fig.6 Surface temperature distribution of the laser side of the specimen at $t = 2.0 \text{ s}$.

Fig.7 Change in temperature distribution along the diagonal AC on the heated surface during the DDL laser irradiation with the shading method.

3.2 Thermal stress distribution

Figure 8 shows the distribution of the 1st principal stress σ_1 on the laser side surface at $t = 2.0 \text{ s}$. The largest principal stress was generated at the center of the area. The first and second principal stresses at the central portion were 113 MPa and 76 MPa , respectively. The stresses were found to be not well balanced. Figure 9 shows the 1st principal stress at the center as a function of normalized thickness Z/Z_0 (Z_0 : thickness). The origin of the Z axis was defined at the front surface. It indicated that the thermal stress was largest at the surface.

3.3 AE measurement

Fig.8 Thermal stress distribution of the 1st principal stress (σ_1) at $t=2s$.

Fig.9 The 1st principal stress at the center vs. normalized thickness.

Figure 10 shows time histories of the temperature difference ΔT ($=|T_1 - T_2|$) extracted from data along the diagonal path A-C, the maximum 1st principal stress at the center and the AE amplitude of the AE signals. The data from channel 4 was plotted for example, because it detected the AE signal with the highest amplitude. The AE generation behavior was observed while the shading effect was maintained (i.e., while $\Delta T > 0$). The maximum 1st principal stress increased with increasing temperature difference between the central and outer region. The AE signals with relatively large amplitude were detected around the time the stress was at its peak. It can be seen that high amplitude AE events were detected at $t = 0.5$ s and at $t = 3.35$ s. Figure 11 shows the two relatively large AE signals. The AE source location is indicated in Fig. 12. The circle size represents the relative AE amplitude. AE source locations in the specimen were characterized by a wide distribution. Also, it was observed that the AE sources with high amplitude were generated between the center and corner A. However, since most of the AE signals in Fig.10 have unclear wavefronts due to the noise, many AE signals were not located. The noise source should be identified and, if possible, reduced in order to locate AE signals in the future.

4. DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Thermal stress

The FEM analysis indicated that the biaxial thermal stress at the center can be induced in the SiC/SiC composites by the DDL irradiation with the shading method. However, the 1st and 2nd principal stresses at the central region were found to be not well balanced. These unbalanced principal stresses can be attributed to the inhomogeneous temperature distribution in the outer region of the sample. The decrease in temperature near two contact surfaces between the rod and the specimen was significant. This indicates that the area of the contact surfaces may be varied between the 4 rods, which would result in unbalanced heat fluxes from the heated sample into the four cold stainless rods. In order to decrease and balance the four heat fluxes into the rods, the contact area must be decreased as much as possible while allowing AE signals to transmit through the contact face without notable attenuation.

Fig.10 Temperature difference ΔT , maximum thermal stress σ_{1_max} , AE amplitude vs. time.

Fig.12 AE Location.

Fig.11 AE signals detected during laser irradiation (a), and during cooling (b).

Fig.13 Relationship between thermal stress $\sigma_1(\sigma_2)$ and shadow radius.

The thermal stress that was obtained with the developed thermal shock test was quantitatively verified by transient thermal analysis using the quarter FEM model. The thermal stress was calculated as a function of the shading radius. The laser irradiation was applied with a constant heat flux for 2.0 seconds. The applied heat flux, q , was obtained as $1.73 \text{ MW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ by the laser power (1.56 kW) multiplied by the emissivity of the composite (1.0) and divided by the laser irradiation area ($0.03 \times 0.03 \text{ m}^2$). The heat transfer rate on the surface is assumed to be $40 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$. Figure 13 shows the comparison of thermal stresses obtained from the ideal boundary condition and the measured boundary conditions. The ideal thermal stresses are indicated as a function of the shadow radius by the solid curve, and the measured thermal stresses σ_1 and σ_2 are indicated by hollow circles at a shadow radius of 3 mm. It was shown that the first and second principal stresses under the experimental conditions were lower than the thermal stress obtained by the ideal boundary condition, but the shade radius was appropriate to induce the near-maximum thermal stress. The lower thermal stress result in the experiment can be attributed to the ununiform temperature distribution in the outer region of the sample. The figure also suggests that the thermal stress under ideal conditions is $\sim 160 \text{ MPa}$ in the composites used in this study.

4.2 Microdamages due to thermal stress

The AE source locations had a wide distribution in the specimen. Figure 14 (1-1 and 2-2) shows the sections where the AE signals with relatively large amplitude were observed. The SEM micrograph of the "1-1" cross section is shown in Fig.15. It indicates that an interlaminar crack between the X and Y fiber bundles was developed at the AE location. The microdamage at "2-2" in Fig.14 was also an interlaminar crack. Since the interlaminar cracks were not observed in the untested specimens, the cracks were initiated due to thermal stress. The location of "1-1" was where the AE signal with the maximum amplitude was located. The AE waveform is shown in the Fig. 11 (b), which starts at $t=3.35s$ during the cooling period. Therefore this suggests the AE waveforms in the Fig. 11 (b) may correlate to the observed interlaminar crack between the X and Y fiber bundles.

The time history of the radial stresses σ_r at the location of "1-1" was shown against the normalized thickness of the specimen in Fig.16. The other stress components were not shown in the figure, because the values were negligibly small. The maximum radial stress at "1-1" is 85 MPa at the front surface ($Z/Z_0=0$) at a time of 2 s. According to the results of the bending test in the previous study [5], the stress of 85 MPa is large enough to initiate a corner crack initiation. However, the corner crack did not propagate along the thickness direction as was observed in the bending test [5], i.e., Z-direction. The difference in the direction of the crack propagation indicates that the unexpected stress component such as "out-of-plane" stress could be induced in this thermal shock test. In order to estimate the out-of-plane stress component, thermal stress will be analyzed with the detail FEM model of 3D-woven structure in the future.

The AE signals with relatively large amplitude were detected around the time the stress was at its peak, which was shown in Fig.10. It also appeared that the AE amplitude was varied with the intensity of the thermal stress σ_{1_max} . However, the AE amplitude depends on the type of the microdamages and the distance to the AE sensor along with the extent of the damage. Thus it is needed to correlate the individual AE waveforms to the type of microdamages in the future. The developed thermal shock test

Fig.14 AE location and observed sections.

Fig.15 SEM micrograph of cross section "11" near laser side surface, showing the interlaminar crack between Y- and X-fiber bundles.

in this study detected the time and location of microdamages with 4ch AE monitoring. If the correlation between AE waveforms and microdamages is found, the type of the microdamages can be identified by this test. If the thermal cycle test is conducted using the thermal shock test, thermal stress and damage development can be monitored simultaneously. With this data, it is expected that the durability of the composites under thermal cycling can be improved.

Fig. 16 Time history of radial stress distribution at the location of "1-1", which was plotted against the normalized thickness.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The thermal shock test method using a direct diode laser (DDL) with 4ch AE monitoring was developed to investigate the thermal stress fracture behavior in SiC/SiC composites. The conclusions are obtained as follows:

- (1) The thermal stress can be easily estimated by FEM analysis using the surface temperature distribution measured by two infrared cameras without using uncertain parameters, such as the heat transfer coefficient. The FEM analysis indicated that the temperature distribution produced a biaxial tensile stress field at the center on the laser-side surface of the sample.
- (2) The observed microdamages due to thermal stress were interlaminar cracks, which were developed between X and Y fiber bundles near the laser-side surface. This suggested that out-of-plane stress was induced.
- (3) AE monitoring can detect the nucleation time and location of the microdamages, both of which correlate to the value of thermal stress. Thus, in this study, the simultaneous evaluation of microdamage progression and thermal stress in the SiC/SiC composites was demonstrated by the DDL thermal shock test with 4ch AE monitoring.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ohnabe H., Masaki S., Onozuka M., Miyahara K. and Sasa T., *Composites, Part A*, **30**, 489-496(1999).
- [2] Suzumura, N., Watanabe, K. Nakamura, T., Araki, T., Natsumura, T., *Ceram. Eng. and Sci. Proc.*, **24**, 4, 621-626 (2003).
- [3] R.Naslain, *Compo. Sci. and Tech.*, **64**, 155-170 (2004).
- [4] Hayashi T. and Wakayama S., *Advanced Composite Materials*, In press.
- [5] Hayashi T. and Wakayama S., *J. Japan Soc. for Comp. Mater.*, **35**, 5, 2009, In press.
- [6] Hasselman D.P.H., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **53**, pp 490-495, 1970.
- [7] Wang H., Singh R.N. and Lowden R.A., *J. Mater. Sci.*, **32**, pp 3305-3313, 1997.
- [8] Kagawa Y., *Compo. Sci. and Tech.*, **57**, pp 607-611, 1997
- [9] Wakayama S., Kobayashi S. and Wada T., *Journal of Acoustic Emission*, **23**, pp 150-155, 2005.
- [10] Akiyama S. and Amada S., *Ceramics International*, **27**, pp 171-177, 2001.
- [11] Takahashi H. and Hashida T., *JSME Inter. J., Series I*, **33**, 3, pp 281-287, 1990.